

Is brown dwarf formation environment-dependent? A case study in NGC 2244

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Brown dwarfs (BDs), objects with masses below $0.075 M_{\odot}$, populate the mass spectrum between the realms of stars and planets, being mainly characterized by their lack of hydrogen burning in their cores. Due to their privileged position, BDs offer a unique window into the unknowns of both worlds and their connection.

Since BDs do not burn hydrogen, they never reach the main sequence and keep evolving with time [1]. The boundary between BDs and stars is located at a spectral type of $\sim M6$ when they are young, and moves down to L-types at field ages. Despite this fundamental difference between stars and BDs, BDs are known to follow a similar early evolutionary path (have disks, outflows, ...), and the distribution of stellar properties (e.g. mass, multiplicity, kinematics and spatial configuration) is shared or has a smooth transition into the BD regime [2]. However, it is still not clear how BDs form. There are several proposed scenarios for their formation [2, and references therein]: like a star, from the turbulent fragmentation of the molecular cloud; like a planet from disk fragmentation, with a later ejection from the system due to some dynamical process. It has also been proposed that BDs form due to the truncation of the mass reservoir of higher-mass objects at earlier stages, thanks to mechanisms such as ejection from the embryo of a multiple system or the photo-erosion of their outer layers by a nearby massive star. At higher masses the general consensus is that most BDs form like stars [3], but it is unknown what happens at lower masses and what is the relative importance of each mechanism. Additionally, the efficiency of the four aforementioned BD formation processes is expected to be affected by the environment where the BD is formed [e.g. 4, 5], so by looking for possible variations of the population of BDs with the environment, the BD dominant formation scenarios can potentially be constrained. In particular, high stellar and gas densities and/or presence of a rich population of OB stars are the main environmental properties that are expected to increase the BD formation efficiency.

The question of the effect of the environmental on BD formation has been addressed by searching for differences in the shape of the initial mass function (IMF) in different star-forming regions. The shape of the low-mass side of the IMF is typically parametrized by a power law ($dN/dM \propto M^{-\alpha}$). In the last two decades, several surveys have taken the task of characterizing the population of nearby star-forming regions down to $\sim 10\text{-}20 M_{Jup}$ [e.g. 6]. These surveys have found the IMF to be universal, with no evident sign of cluster-to-cluster variation.

The IMF of these clusters is characterized by $\alpha = 0.6\text{--}1$, and it was found that for each new BD between 2 and 5 stars are formed [7, and references therein]. But the environment of these nearby star-forming regions is defined by low stellar densities and few to none OB stars, which are the main expected environmental drivers of variations in BD formation efficiency. In order to test whether BD formation is affected by its birth environment, we have started a program to study various young clusters characterized by different environmental properties in terms of stellar density and number of OB stars. In this contribution I discussed our preliminary results on the spectroscopic low-mass IMF of the core of NGC 2244, a 2 Myr old cluster located at 1.5 kpc, whose environment is characterized by low stellar densities (similar to nearby star-forming regions) and a rich population of OB stars, therefore being the perfect laboratory where to study the effect of OB stars on BD formation.

Observations and analysis

[7] presented a deep NIR photometric study of the core region of the young cluster NGC 2244. In this contribution we studied the low-mass population of the same region but using spectroscopy at the lower masses.

Figure 1: Three of the low-mass members of NGC 2244 with KMOS spectra together with their best fit template.

At higher masses ($0.3\text{--}1.2 M_{\odot}$) we used the member list of Muzic et al. (submitted), where we studied the objects to belong to the entire Rosette nebula by applying the Probabilistic Random Forest (PRF) algorithm using

as input optical to near infrared photometry as well as proper motions from *Gaia* EDR3. We also used archival VIMOS/VLT optical spectroscopy, where the membership came from H- α emission above the accretion threshold.

At lower masses ($<0.3 M_{\odot}$) we obtained near infrared spectroscopy of 85 objects using KMOS/VLT. The spectra were obtained using the *HK* filter ($\sim 1.5\text{--}2.4 \mu\text{m}$), which has a mean spectral resolving power of ~ 1800 . We found 38 of these objects to present a broad shape consistent with being low-mass stars or BDs. For these 38 objects we derived their spectral type and extinction by comparison with spectral templates (see Figure 1).

In order to be confirmed as members they have to present some signature arguing for their youth. We evaluated their youth using gravity-sensitive spectral indices based on the H-band peak feature [8]. We found 32 bona-fide members (M2-M8.5), including, to our knowledge, the first spectroscopically confirmed BDs beyond 1 kpc. In the KMOS brightness range ($J=16.5\text{--}19$ mag), we completed the census of cluster members that were not observed with KMOS by estimating the number of unobserved members using the success rate of the spectroscopic follow up.

Results

Using the compiled member list, we obtained the IMF of the cluster (see Figure 2). The IMF can be fitted by a broken power law, with a mass break at $0.4 M_{\odot}$. At higher masses we found a slope of 2.08 ± 0.06 , which is consistent with the Salpeter slope ($\alpha = 2.35$). At lower masses we found a slope of 1.21 ± 0.13 . This slope is at the steeper side of the typical values found in nearby star-forming regions ($\alpha = 0.6\text{--}1$), although still in agreement within errors. Comparing these results to that obtained in the photometry-only study of the same cluster [1.02 ± 0.04 , 7], we found the new α value to be consistent within errors.

We also evaluated the BD formation efficiency of the cluster through the star/BD ratio, and found this value to be 2.36 ± 0.48 . The star/BD ratio of nearby star-forming regions (2–5) is calculated between $0.03\text{--}0.1 M_{\odot}$, while we estimate that we are only complete down to $\sim 0.045 M_{\odot}$ (see Figure 2), so the derived value is an upper limit of the true value. We also found an indication that the lower mass BDs ($<0.045 M_{\odot}$) are in average closer to the OB stars of the region, but this result can be a bias of

the observed KMOS sample and we are missing a significant fraction of the objects at those masses.

Figure 2: Derived IMF of NGC 2244 together with the fit of a broken-power law, and the estimated completeness of the population ($\sim 0.045 M_{\odot}$).

Summary

We studied the low-mass population of the core region of NGC 2244, a massive young cluster characterized by a rich population of OB stars, in order to test the effect of OB stars on BD formation. We identified 32 new low-mass members of the cluster using near infrared spectroscopy. We found the slope of the low-mass IMF of the region to be steeper than the typical locus of values, although in agreement within the errors. The presented preliminary results could potentially hint BD overproduction on NGC 2244 and calls for the attention of further studies of the region.

References

- [1] Burrows, A., et al., 2001, *RvMP*, 73, 719
- [2] Luhman, K., 2012, *ARA&A*, 50, 65
- [3] Luhman, K., et al., 2007, *Protostars and Planets V*, 443
- [4] Whitworth, A. P., & Zinnecker, H., 2004, *A&A*, 427, 299
- [5] Bonnell, I. A., et al., 2008, *MNRAS*, 389, 1556
- [6] Esplin, T., & Luhman, K., 2019, *AJ*, 158, 54
- [7] Muzic, K., et al., 2019, *ApJ*, 881, 79
- [8] Almendros-Abad, V., et al., 2022, *A&A*, 657, 129

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